

Article

Manufacturing Process and Characteristics of Silica Nanostructures for Anti-Reflection at 355 nm

Anne Gärtner ^{1,2,*} , Ulrike Schulz ¹, Astrid Bingel ¹, Sven Schröder ¹, Tomáš Mocek ³ and Andreas Tünnermann ^{1,2}

¹ Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Optics and Precision Engineering IOF, Albert-Einstein-Str. 7, 07745 Jena, Germany

² Abbe Center of Photonics, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Albert-Einstein-Str. 6, 07745 Jena, Germany

³ HiLASE Centre, Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Za Radnici 828, 252 41 Dolní Břežany, Czech Republic; muresan@hilase.cz (M.-G.M.)

* Correspondence: anne.gaertner@iof.fraunhofer.de

Abstract: Recent advancements in photonics have intensified the performance requirements for optical systems and present significant challenges for optical coating technologies. Conventional interference coating systems often prove to be insufficient, especially in applications requiring large angles of light incidence or a wide wavelength range. Nanostructures, which consist of an air material mixture, offer promising alternatives. In this work, silica nanostructures are manufactured by the AR-plas2 method, in which first an organic layer is evaporated onto a substrate. This organic layer forms self-organizing nanostructures by a plasma etching step, which are subsequently coated with silica. Finally, the organic residues are removed by additional plasma etching and heat treatment steps, which results in hollow silica structures. The work examines the optical and functional properties of these structures designed for 355 nm to demonstrate their use as anti-reflective coatings for advanced optical systems.

Keywords: anti-reflective; nanostructures; absorption; light scattering; power spectral density function; laser-induced damage threshold

Academic Editors: Tsvetanka Babeva, Gergana Alexieva and Rositsa Gergova

Received: 31 March 2025

Revised: 23 April 2025

Accepted: 28 April 2025

Published: 6 May 2025

Citation: Gärtner, A.; Mureşan, M.-G.; Mühlig, C.; Herffurth, T.; Felde, N.; Wagner, H.; Schulz, U.; Bingel, A.; Schröder, S.; Mocek, T.; et al. Manufacturing Process and Characteristics of Silica Nanostructures for Anti-Reflection at 355 nm. *Coatings* **2025**, *15*, 556. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings15050556>

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

The rapid development in photonics opens new perspectives for future technologies, particularly in areas such as quantum computing, laser material processing, or semiconductor technology. However, these innovations also require increasingly sophisticated optical systems. That means they must be suitable, e.g., for high laser powers, withstand ultra-high vacuum conditions, address multiple wavelengths simultaneously, or guarantee outstanding optical performance even at high angles of light incidence.

The challenges are particularly evident in systems that utilize ultraviolet (UV) light. Not only is the choice of materials limited, but interactions between UV light and materials can also lead to unwanted absorption, which may result in the destruction of optical components. Anti-reflective (AR) coatings in particular play a key role here, as they not only have to provide excellent optical performance but are often the weakest element in such systems [1–3]. The choice of materials and manufacturing processes is particularly important here and should be chosen carefully [4]. For example, optical systems that operate with lasers with a wavelength of 355 nm are of technical importance as they are used in many fields, e.g., semiconductor technology or material processing. That is why several research groups have developed AR coating systems for this wavelength. Hafnia,

as a material with a high refractive index in combination with silica (SiO_2), has proven itself as a coating system with a high laser-induced damage threshold and has been investigated by different groups [1,4–8]. Juškevičius et al. [5], for example, present an AR system that consists of silica and hafnia that was applied on fused silica using e-beam coating technology. The coating system achieves a reflection of less than 0.2% at 355 nm and a laser-induced damage threshold (LIDT) of 6.8 J/cm^2 on non-etched fused silica (measurement wavelength: 355 nm; 1-on-1 test according to [9]; pulse duration: 3 ns; repetition rate: 15 Hz; Nd:YAG laser). Falmbigl et al. [1] investigated a double-sided coated AR coating system on fused silica, also consisting of silica and hafnia, produced by ion beam sputtering. They achieved transmission values above 99.8% at 355 nm. Absorption was measured using photothermal common-path interferometry, and they achieved a value of around 110 ppm. The LIDT value was measured with 15.7 J/cm^2 (measurement wavelength: 355 nm; 200-on-1 test; pulse duration: 8 ns; repetition rate: 20 Hz). However, LIDT values could only be compared with each other when the same substrate or measurement parameters were used, because they depend on various factors, including the choice of coating method, the material quality and surface condition of the substrate [10–12]. Consequently, a more meaningful evaluation of the LIDT values is achieved by comparing them with those of the uncoated substrate, an approach that is employed in this study.

The use of commercial interference coating systems to minimize unwanted reflections has its limitations, as they are often unable to meet the new requirements for optical components due to the limited choice of materials and therefore predefined refractive indices. An alternative is offered by nanostructures, in which an air material mixture creates an effective refractive index that can be optimally adapted to the design [13–19]. Several studies show that the combination of interference coatings and nanostructures or the combination of more than one nanostructure provide improved optical performance [20,21]. In addition, the LIDT can be higher than that of interference coatings. This was already demonstrated in a round robin experiment in 2010, in which wet-chemically produced sol gel coatings exhibited the highest LIDT values for a wavelength of 355 nm [4]. Another experiment was performed by Tolenis et al. They compared nanostructures that were produced using glancing angle deposition (GLAD) technology, with a coating based on silica and hafnia made by ion beam sputtering (IBS); both were deposited on fused silica [22]. They achieved a reflection of 0.2% for the GLAD structures and 0.3% for the silica/hafnia coating system at 355 nm. They showed that the LIDT of the GLAD structures was 16.8 J/cm^2 compared to 5.1 J/cm^2 for the IBS manufactured coating (measurement wavelength: 355 nm; 1-on-1 test according to [9]; pulse duration: 3.1 ns; repetition rate: 15 Hz; Nd:YAG laser). Other processes to produce nanostructures besides wet-chemical coating processes [23] are described in the literature, e.g., lithographic processes [24,25], reactive ion etching [26–28] or production using physical vapor deposition technology [7,22,29]. In this paper, nanostructures made of silica are fabricated using AR-plas2 technology, which uses a commercially available chamber for physical vapor deposition equipped with an advanced plasma source (APS). This technology is cost-effective and suitable for mass production. A major advantage of this approach is the production of layer systems within one coating process, where nanostructures can be combined with interference layer systems, but also several structures with each other. This results in improved layer systems that meet the increasing requirements, e.g., for optical broadband systems. The method was originally developed for etching polymer surfaces and later adapted to the structuring of organic layers. For this, an organic transfer layer is deposited onto an arbitrary substrate. Subsequently, self-assembling nanostructures are formed by plasma etching, which are then overcoated with silica. The organic components can be removed by additional post-treatment steps, resulting in hollow silica nanostructures.

Due to the technical importance of optical systems with lasers for 355 nm mentioned at the beginning, nanostructures with an AR effect for 355 nm were produced and investigated in this work. Since they have a higher roughness due to their morphology, which in turn leads to higher optical losses, a structural analysis was conducted in addition to the examination of optical properties. The organic material used was Xanthine, which forms nanostructures after plasma etching and has already been introduced in a previous work [30]. Most of the organic material was removed by additional treatment steps, resulting in hollow silica structures. To investigate whether residual organic material was still in the structures, absorption and LIDT measurements were conducted.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Sample Preparation

The nanostructures were designed for the wavelength of 355 nm and double-sided coated on SK-1300 (Ohara, Japan) glass with a 1 inch diameter and 1 mm thickness. There were no specific requirements for the substrate quality. The substrates were pre-cleaned using ethanol and subsequently cleaned in an ultrasonic bath.

The commercial coating chamber SyrusPro 1100 (Bühler AG, Alzenau, Germany) was used for the AR-plas2 method. The chamber is equipped with an APS to support chemical and physical reactions, a thermal evaporator to deposit organic materials, and an electron beam gun for oxide materials. During the process, a homogeneous Xanthine (Sigma-Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) layer was first deposited from a molybdenum boat onto the substrate at an initial chamber pressure of 2×10^{-5} mbar. The deposition of the organic material was controlled by optical monitoring to achieve a thickness of 145 nm. Subsequent etching with the APS and an O_2/Ar gas mixture led to self-assembling nanostructure formation, which was coated with 32 nm of silica [30]. It is assumed that both chemical transformation and physical removal led to the formation of the structures. The organic part of nanostructure was removed by subsequent annealing and a standard wet-cleaning procedure, resulting in hollow silica nanostructures.

2.2. Topographical Measurements and Analysis

Roughness analysis was performed using an atomic force microscope (AFM) Dimension Icon (Bruker, CA, USA) and a white light interferometer (WLI) NewView 7300 (ZygoLOT Europe GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany). Using AFM measurements, roughness was analyzed for spatial frequencies from $0.02 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ to $256 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, corresponding to scan areas from $(50 \times 50) \mu\text{m}^2$ to $(1 \times 1) \mu\text{m}^2$. WLI measurements were performed for $5\times$ to $50\times$ magnification to calculate the roughness for spatial frequencies down to $0.001 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. By combining the different roughness measurement methods and areas, roughness information can be analyzed for a wide range of surface structures. Therefore, a quantitative evaluation of the data was performed by calculating the two-dimensional power spectral density (PSD) function for each measurement according to the following formula:

$$PSD(f_x, f_y) = \lim_{L \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{L^2} \left| \int_{-\frac{L}{2}}^{\frac{L}{2}} \int_{-\frac{L}{2}}^{\frac{L}{2}} (h(x, y) e^{-2\pi i(f_x x + f_y y)}) dx dy \right|^2, \quad (1)$$

where $h(x,y)$ represents the topographical surface data, L the scan size and f_x and f_y the spatial frequency components. The PSD function (Equation (1)) describes the relative strength of the individual roughness components in terms of spatial frequencies and thus consider not only the vertical, but also the lateral distribution of the measured topography

data [31]. In addition, a scanning electron microscope (SEM) from Zeiss SIGMA SEM was used to magnify the structures.

For the ex situ characterization after laser damage tests of the samples, an OLX-5000 (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) confocal laser scanning microscope was used, and the images were evaluated using the open-source software package Gwyddion (version 2.66) [32].

2.3. Reflectance, Transmission, Absorption, and Light Scattering Measurements

To investigate the optical performance, transmission (T) and reflection (R) have been measured with a UV/VIS spectrophotometer Lambda 950 (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA) at an angle of light incidence of 6° . A special inset was used to measure absolute R and T values of the samples without changing its position [33]. The accuracy of the instrument is given with 0.1% in the visible and 0.2% in the UV spectral range.

Light scattering properties of the nanostructures were quantified by angle-resolved light scattering measurements (ARS; for measurement geometry, see Figure 1) using a 3D scatterometer (system MLS10, developed at Fraunhofer IOF). The ARS is defined as the scattered power (ΔP_s) into the solid angle $\Delta\Omega_s$ as a function of the scattering angles θ_s and φ_s , normalized to this solid angle and the incident light power (P_i).

Figure 1. Light scattering measurement geometry in transmission direction, similar in reflection hemisphere (θ_i —angle of light incidence; θ_s , φ_s —polar and azimuthal scattering angles; $\Delta\Omega_s$ —solid angle).

Considering the scattering over the entire hemisphere for backward and forward direction, the numerical integration of the ARS, excluding specular reflection/transmission, gives the total scattering (TS = P_s/P_i) over the whole hemisphere. TS can be calculated by the integration from the measured ARS, which is scattered into the forward or backward hemispheres. At normal incidence, scattering angles of $2^\circ \leq \theta_s \leq 85^\circ$ must be considered for the measurement of TS (according to the ISO 13696 standard) [34]. A description of the set-up for the light scattering measurements can be found in [35]. The uncertainty is given with 10%.

Absolute absorption (A) measurements were performed using the laser-induced deflection method. This method utilizes a photothermal technique with a transverse pump sample beam configuration. For the samples, a modified measurement concept was used, the so-called thin disc vertical concept. Further details are provided in [36].

The measurements for light scattering and absorption were performed at 355 nm.

2.4. Laser-Induced Damage Threshold (LIDT) Measurements

The laser-induced damage threshold (LIDT) measurements were conducted using a previously described set-up [37]. This set-up operates in an ISO class 6 clean room under

ambient conditions and uses a tripled Q-Smart 450 (Lumibird, Lannion, France) system as the laser source. A schematic of the LIDT set-up is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Schematics of the LIDT measurement set-up used to measure the 1-on-1, 10-on-1, and R-on-1 test types.

All tests were conducted with a linearly polarized (p-polarization) pulse with a duration of 8.5 ns in the third harmonic (355 nm) of the neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet (Nd:YAG) laser and a frequency of 10 Hz. The beam diameter, which was fitted with a Gaussian profile at $1/e^2$, varied between 82 and 174 μm . The greatest contribution to the overall error budget was represented by the pulse-to-pulse energy stability and the beam profiler accuracy. The combined error contribution to the tests was calculated to be approximately $\pm 8\%$. The LIDT tests were performed in compliance with ISO 21254 [9,38–40], using the 1-on-1, S-on-1, and R-on-1 methods.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Morphological and Surface Analysis

Figure 3 shows the SEM images of the silica nanostructures. In the cross-sectional image (Figure 3a) it can be seen, that columnar structures have been formed. The top view indicates that the structures are stochastically distributed over the surface (Figure 3b).

Figure 3. Cross-sectional (a) and top-view (b) SEM images of the silica nanostructures.

In addition to SEM images, topographical data were assessed using AFM and WLI for a quantitative evaluation of the surface by calculating the PSD functions. To capture information over a broad range of spatial frequencies, measurements were conducted in various measurement areas. Exemplarily, AFM images for a $(1 \times 1) \mu\text{m}^2$ scan area are given in Figure 4.

Figure 4. AFM images of the silica nanostructures and uncoated substrate.

The power spectral density (PSD) function is a technique for analyzing the distribution of surface roughness over different spatial frequencies. Rather than just average roughness values (e.g., average roughness (Ra) or root mean square roughness (rms)), which only provide a single value containing the vertical information of the surface, the PSD function provides a more comprehensive view by adding lateral information of the surface features in terms of their frequency components. This provides a better understanding of how the anti-reflective coating interacts with light at different wavelengths (e.g., in terms of light scattering) and can identify corresponding optical behavior. Particularly for light scattering the spatial frequencies are directly linked to the scattering direction by the grating equations. The corresponding PSD functions were evaluated (as described in Section 2.2) and combined by geometrically averaging, resulting in a so-called Master PSD function [21]. This approach not only allowed for the analysis of the scattering-relevant spatial frequency range but also provided insights into the structures at both high and low spatial frequencies. This enabled us to evaluate the influence of the coatings on substrate roughness and, consequently, the overall morphology of the samples. The Master PSD functions for both the nanostructure and the uncoated substrate, are shown in Figure 5. Figure 5a) also shows the spatial frequency range relevant for light scattering at a wavelength of 355 nm. The Master PSD function reveals an almost perfect replication of the substrate roughness below $f = 0.1 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, which is typical for thin films with low intrinsic roughness. A difference to the substrate occurs in the mid- and high-spatial-frequency range, which can be attributed to the nanostructure, where the roughness becomes relevant. However, it should be noted that only particle-free areas were considered for the roughness analysis. When particles are taken into account, the roughness increases drastically, as can be seen in Figure 5b), which shows the PSD functions for particle-free and contaminated surface areas. The origin of the particles is currently unknown and is already being investigated in more detail.

Figure 5. Master PSD functions of an uncoated substrate (black line) and the silica nanostructures (orange line, (a)). Comparison between the Master PSD functions of nanostructures on a clean position (straight line) compared to a position with a particle (dotted line, (b)).

3.2. Optical Properties and the Calculation of the Effective Refractive Index

Figure 6 shows the corresponding R and T (a) spectra of a double-sided coated substrate and an uncoated substrate, and the optical losses (b), which were calculated by subtracting R and T from 100%. The wavelength range for the measurements was between 300 nm and 400 nm.

Figure 6. Reflectance and transmittance measurements (a) and optical losses (b) for an uncoated substrate (black line), and the double-sided coated silica nanostructures (orange line).

The nanostructures show a transmission value of 99.8% and a reflectance value of 0.1% at a design wavelength of 355 nm (see Figure 6a). This is comparable to the value of the system of interference layers given by Falmbigl et al. [1]. The minimum/maximum is shifted to 370 nm. However, the curve can be shifted to shorter wavelengths by further adjusting the coating parameters. The optical losses for the nanostructures are approximately 0.1% at 355 nm (see Figure 6b), which may contain contributions from both light scattering and absorption. However, since the noise of the measuring device prevents the exact determination of the losses, light scattering and absorption were measured separately according to the methods described in Section 2.3. The results are also given in this section.

To calculate the effective refractive index (n_{eff}), a three-layer model was assumed by reverse data fitting with OptiRe software (version 13.77, OptiLayer GmbH, Ismaning, Germany) using the spectra (Figure 6) and the heights extracted from microscope images

taken with the SEM. For this purpose, the structures were divided into three areas and their corresponding n_{eff} values were estimated (see Figure 7). A height of 40 nm with an n_{eff} of 1.15 is calculated for H1, as well as a height of 20 nm and an n_{eff} of 1.3 for H2 and a height of 15 nm with an n_{eff} of 1.05 for H3. As the structures are not the same height and the material is not equally distributed, this calculation is subject to errors and is therefore only a first approximation.

Figure 7. Sketch of the three-layer model to calculate the effective refractive index (n_{eff}) of the silica nanostructures. The calculation is a first approximation, due to measurement errors, with the following results: H1 with 40 nm height and n_{eff} of 1.15, H2 with 20 nm height and n_{eff} of 1.3, and H3 with 15 nm height and n_{eff} of 1.05.

Light scattering depends on different properties of the coating, e.g., the surface structure, but also volume effects or material properties (e.g., refractive index). However, the surface itself has the greatest influence. Figure 8 shows the ARS curve for the structure including the uncoated substrate. In addition, the corresponding calculated TS value for the silica nanostructures is (1652 ± 165) ppm, and it is (209 ± 21) ppm for the uncoated substrate.

Figure 8. ARS measurements at 355 nm for an angle of light incidence of 6° for an uncoated substrate (black line) and the silica nanostructures (orange line).

The curves in Figure 8 display distinct peaks at -180° and 0° , corresponding to the directions of specular transmission and reflection, respectively. When evaluating the residual scatter signal in the off-specular direction, an increase in both the back and front scattering directions is observed for the nanostructures compared to the scattering from the substrate. However, based on the examination of the structural properties (see SEM images in Figure 3), a lower TS value would have been expected, as the heights of the single columns are regular and not clustered. Looking again at the ARS curves in Figure 8,

oscillations can be recognized for the nanostructures both in the near-and far-angle range. This indicates light scattering induced by particles, which is particularly evident in the forward scattering [41].

The absorption value for the nanostructures was determined to be (166.8 ± 15.0) ppm. This value can be attributed to the residual organic material, which was used during the manufacturing process and can still be contained within the silica structures.

3.3. Laser-Induced Damage Threshold (LIDT) Results

Each sample was tested within 80% of the clear aperture using a closed hexagonal pattern with 127 positions placed 1.55 mm from each other, thus fulfilling the general recommendation for the distribution to prevent cross contamination. For the 1-on-1 and S-on-1 tests, where S is 10, 10 positions with the same fluence were tested for statistical purposes, while 24 positions were tested in the R-on-1 test. For the latter, each position was initially irradiated with a maximum of 100 pulses at a constant fluence. Subsequently, the fluence was increased by 0.5 J/cm^2 and the sample was irradiated once more with a maximum of 100 pulses until the surface showed visible signs of destruction. The results for all tests are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the LIDT values.

Sample	1-on-1 [J/cm^2]	10-on-1 [J/cm^2]	R-on-1 [J/cm^2]
Nanostructure	4.38 ± 0.34	2.87 ± 0.20	1.37 ± 0.42
Substrate	6.49 ± 0.50	4.26 ± 0.30	2.28 ± 0.59

The results of the 1-on-1 test indicate that the nanostructures show lower LIDT values to the substrate. Furthermore, the 1-on-1 methodology test provides insights into the fundamental damage mechanisms of the given material. Using high-resolution laser scanning microscopy, different damage morphologies could be distinguished between the nanostructures and the substrate, as shown in Figure 9. Only damaged positions of fluences exceeding the LIDT were considered in the study. For the silica nanostructures, a damage pattern is shown at a fluence of 11.58 J/cm^2 , while for the uncoated substrate, damage is shown at 24.77 J/cm^2 .

Based on the crater depth analysis in Figure 9, it can be seen that the silica nanostructure and the substrate presented different forms of melting and resolidification of the material, either from the coating or in combination with the glass substrate [42]. In addition, the material ejected from the crater is deposited in the nearby zone, visible in the slight color change, in form of a halo around the crater. For the nanostructures, the crater depth exceeded the coating thickness, reaching depths between 150 and 300 μm .

As the results of the 10-on-1 test show, the LIDT values are lower than the values observed in the 1-on-1 test, which was anticipated. Figure 10 presents the microscopic images of the damage morphologies for the samples. The damage morphology of the nanostructures shows a few small circumferential cracks besides melting. There are no cracks, which might be related to the increased absorption. The analyzed surface spot on the substrate was irradiated with an intensity of 12.15 J/cm^2 and exhibited indications of profound ablation that has overcome the melting phase, which is characteristic for bare substrates or crystals.

Figure 9. Damage morphology for the nanostructure and uncoated substrate, showing the microscope image with an inset for more details, and the crater depth for the 1-on-1 LIDT test.

Figure 10. Microscopic images for the damage morphology of the silica nanostructure and the uncoated substrate after 10-on-1 LIDT test.

Although a 0.5 J/cm^2 step and 100 pulses for each fluence were selected for the R-on-1 test, the results shown in Table 1 represent the mean LIDT value obtained from 24 individual positions. Looking at the uncoated substrate, a standard deviation of around 25% from the mean value can be seen, whereas the standard deviation for the nanostructures is around 30%. This may be related to small inhomogeneities in the substrate, which can cause local absorption points that are known to lower the LIDT value, especially in the nanosecond regime. In addition, organic residues in the nanostructures can reduce the LIDT, which may correlate with the absorption values in Section 3.2. Figure 11 shows an overview where damage occurred after the nanostructure and the uncoated substrate were irradiated with different fluences. Additionally, damage is found on both the front and back of all samples. The front side presents marks of pulse accumulation and the respective crater formation. The craters tended to be relative large in size and presented marks of molten materials

and cracks/flaking from the edges [43]. The damage on the rear side can be explained by the Fresnel diffraction by contamination particles, surface imperfections, and perhaps by the nanostructures themselves [44]. No conditional effects could be identified in the tested samples.

Figure 11. Distribution of all illumination spots where damage occurred for the R-on-1 test depending on the fluences for the silica nanostructures and uncoated substrate. The graph only consider values at which damage occurred and excludes damage below 0.5 J/cm².

Although the values are generally lower than those reported in the literature, it should be mentioned that the LIDT depends on various factors, such as the surface quality. Therefore, the values should always be compared with the LIDT of the uncoated substrate, which is the highest achievable LIDT.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we successfully produced hollow silica nanostructures specifically designed for a wavelength of 355 nm. The achieved transmittance of 99.8% shows very good optical performance suitable for anti-reflective coatings. The optical properties were described with a model consisting of three layers and calculated by reverse data fitting using transmittance and reflectance spectra. The surface roughness, formed by the thickened heads of the columns, exhibited an rms value of 3.7 nm. A PSD analysis revealed that the roughness of the nanostructures in the mid- and high-frequency range differs from that of the uncoated substrate, as the roughness of the nanostructures only becomes relevant in these ranges. In the low-spatial-frequency range (below 0.1 μm), the Master PSD function shows almost perfect agreement with the substrate roughness, which is typical for thin films with low intrinsic roughness. The total scattering, approximately 1652 ppm, absorption losses of around 170 ppm and the comparatively low LIDT value are presumably due to residual organics in the silica structures. Further reduction of the organics, e.g., by solvents, is currently being investigated. After optimization, the AR-plas2 process seems promising for producing UV laser-resistant AR coatings.

Author Contributions: Methodology, A.G., M.-G.M., C.M., N.F. and H.W.; Investigation, A.G., C.M., N.F. and H.W.; Writing—original draft, A.G., M.-G.M. and N.F.; Writing—review & editing, A.G., M.-G.M., C.M., T.H., H.W., U.S., A.B., S.S., T.M. and A.T. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) as part of the funding program Photonics Research Germany (project Qzell, contract number 13N15957), and the European Union and state budget of the Czech Republic under the project LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004573.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Data are contained within the article.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Falmbigl, M.; Godin, K.; George, J.; Mühligh, C.; Rubin, B. Effect of annealing on properties and performance of HfO₂/SiO₂ optical coatings for UV-applications. *Opt. Express* **2022**, *30*, 12326–12336. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
2. Jensen, L. *Laserinduzierte Zerstörung in Oxidischen Schichtsystemen für den UV Bereich*; Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover: Hannover, Germany, 2014.
3. Arnold, B.M.; Rashvand, C.; Willis, L.; Dabney, M.S. UV fatigue of laser optics: Laser-induced contamination. *Laser-Induc. Damage Opt. Mater.* **2022**, *2022*, 12300.
4. Stolz, C.J.; Caputo, M.; Griffin, A.J.; Thomas, M.D. BDS thin film UV antireflection laser damage competition. *Laser-Induc. Damage Opt. Mater.* **2010**, *2010*, 7842.
5. Juškevičius, K.; Buzelis, R.; Abromavičius, G.; Samuilovas, R.; Abbas, S.; Belosludtsev, A.; Drazdys, R.; Kičas, S. Argon plasma etching of fused silica substrates for manufacturing high laser damage resistance optical interference coatings. *Opt. Mater. Express* **2017**, *7*, 3598–3607. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Alam, S.; Paul, P.; Beladiya, V.; Schmitt, P.; Stenzel, O.; Trost, M.; Wilbrandt, S.; Mühligh, C.; Schröder, S.; Matthäus, G.; et al. Heterostructure films of SiO₂ and HfO₂ for high-power laser optics prepared by plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition. *Coatings* **2023**, *13*, 278. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Weiss, M.; Davenport, A.; Lucas, S.C.; Pamedytytė, D.; Galinis, J.; Melninkaitis, A.; Siehien, J.; Siehien, W.; Chicoine, M.; Schiettekatte, F.; et al. Laser damage of UV hafnia-based multilayer dielectric coatings at 355 nm wavelength. *Laser-Induc. Damage Opt. Mater.* **2024**, *2024*, 13190.
8. Yin, C.; Zhu, M.; Zeng, T.; Song, C.; Chai, Y.; Shao, Y.; Zhang, R.; Zhao, J.; Li, D.; Shao, J. HfO₂/SiO₂ anti-reflection films for UV lasers via plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition. *J. Alloys Compd.* **2021**, *859*, 157875. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. *ISO 21254-1:2011*; Lasers and Laser-Related equipment—Test Methods for Laser-Radiation-Induced Damage Threshold—Part 1: Definitions and General Principles. International Organization for Standardization: London, UK, 2011.
10. Lyngnes, O.; Ode, A.; Ness, D.C. Anti-reflection coating damage threshold dependence on substrate material. In *Laser-Induced Damage in Optical Materials*; SPIE: Bellingham, WA, USA, 2009; Volume 7504.
11. Zhu, M.; Xing, H.; Chai, Y.; Yi, K.; Sun, J.; Wang, J.; Shao, J. Improving the laser-induced damage threshold of 532-nm antireflection coating using plasma ion cleaning. *Opt. Eng.* **2017**, *56*, 011003. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Hobbs, D.S. Laser damage threshold measurements of anti-reflection microstructures operating in the near UV and mid-infrared. In *Laser-Induced Damage in Optical Materials*; SPIE: Bellingham, WA, USA, 2010; Volume 7842.
13. Chen, M.; Chang, H.C.; Chang, A.S.; Lin, S.Y.; Xi, J.Q.; Schubert, E.F. Design of optical path for wide-angle gradient-index antireflection coatings. *Appl. Opt.* **2007**, *46*, 6533–6538. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Xi, J.Q.; Schubert, M.F.; Kim, J.K.; Schubert, E.F.; Chen, M.; Lin, S.Y.; Liu, W.; Smart, J.A. Optical thin-film materials with low refractive index for broadband elimination of Fresnel reflection. *Nat. Photonics* **2007**, *1*, 176–179. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Dobrowolski, J.A.; Poitras, D.; Ma, P.; Vakil, H.; Acree, M. Toward perfect antireflection coatings: Numerical investigation. *Appl. Opt.* **2002**, *41*, 3075–3083. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
16. Minot, M.J. The angular reflectance of single-layer gradient refractive-index films. *J. Opt. Soc. Am.* **1977**, *67*, 1046–1050. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Southwell, W.H. Gradient-index antireflection coatings. *Opt. Lett.* **1983**, *8*, 584–586. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
18. Southwell, W.H. Pyramid-array surface-relief structures producing antireflection index matching on optical surfaces. *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* **1991**, *8*, 549–553. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Brunner, R.; Sandfuchs, O.; Pacholski, C.; Morhard, C.; Spatz, J. Lessons from nature: Biomimetic subwavelength structures for high-performance optics. *Laser Photonics Rev.* **2012**, *6*, 641–659. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Bruynooghe, S.; Schulze, M.; Helgert, M.; Challier, M.; Tordova, D.; Sundermann, M.; Koch, T.; Gatto, A.; Kley, E.-B. Broadband and wide-angle hybrid antireflection coatings prepared by combining interference multilayers with subwavelength structures. *J. Nanophotonics* **2016**, *10*, 033002. [[CrossRef](#)]

21. Chhajed, S.; Schubert, M.F.; Kim, J.K.; Schubert, E.F. Nanostructured multilayer graded-index antireflection coating for Si solar cells with broadband and omnidirectional characteristics. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2008**, *93*, 251108. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Tolenis, T.; Grinevičiūtė, L.; Buzelis, R.; Smalakys, L.; Pupka, E.; Melnikas, S.; Selskis, A.; Drazdys, R.; Melninkaitis, A. Sculptured anti-reflection coatings for high power lasers. *Opt. Mater. Express* **2017**, *7*, 1249–1258. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Chi, F.; Pan, N.; Ding, C.; Wang, X.; Yi, F.; Li, X.; Lei, J. Ultraviolet laser-induced damage of freestanding silica nanoparticle films. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2019**, *463*, 566–572. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Ting, C.-J.; Chen, C.-F.; Chou, C. Subwavelength structures for broadband antireflection application. *Opt. Commun.* **2009**, *282*, 434–438. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Wang, S.; Yu, X.Z.; Fan, H.T. Simple lithographic approach for subwavelength structure antireflection. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2007**, *91*, 061105. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Hobbs, D.S.; MacLeod, B.D. High laser damage threshold surface relief micro-structures for anti-reflection applications. *Laser-Induc. Damage Opt. Mater.* **2007**, *2007*, 6720.
27. Okabe, T.; Yano, T.; Yatagawa, K.; Taniguchi, J. Polyimide moth-eye nanostructures formed by oxygen ion beam etching for anti-reflection layers. *Microelectron. Eng.* **2021**, *242*, 111559. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Barlow, A.J.; Sano, N.; Murdoch, B.J.; Portoles, J.F.; Pigram, P.J.; Cumpson, P.J. Observing the evolution of regular nanostructured indium phosphide after gas cluster ion beam etching. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2018**, *459*, 678–685. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Prachachet, R.; Horprathum, M.; Eiamchai, P.; Limwichean, S.; Chananonawathorn, C.; Samransuksamer, B.; Lertvanithphol, T.; Buranasiri, P.; Muthitamongkol, P.; Boonruang, S. A comparative study on omnidirectional anti-reflection SiO₂ nanostructure films coating by glancing angle deposition. *Oxide-Based Mater. Devices IX* **2018**, *2018*, 10533.
30. Gärtner, A.; Seifert, T.; Rickelt, F.; Schulz, U.; Tünnermann, A. Xanthine: A promising organic material for the development of nanostructured anti-reflective layers. *Adv. Opt. Thin Film. VII* **2021**, *2021*, 11872.
31. Duparré, A.; Ferre-Borrull, J.; Gliech, S.; Notni, G.; Steinert, J.; Bennett, J.M. Surface characterization techniques for determining the root-mean-square roughness and power spectral densities of optical components. *Appl. Opt.* **2002**, *41*, 154–171. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Nečas, D.; Klapetek, P. Gwyddion: An open-source software for SPM data analysis. *Open Phys.* **2012**, *10*, 181–188. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Wilbrandt, S.; Stenzel, O. In Situ and Ex Situ Spectrophotometric Characterization of Single- and Multilayer-Coatings II: Experimental Technique and Application Examples. In *Optical Characterization of Thin Solid Films*; Springer International Publishing: Cham, Switzerland, 2018; pp. 203–232.
34. Stover, J. *Optical Scattering: Measurement and Analysis*, 3rd ed.; SPIE: Bellingham, WA, USA, 2012.
35. Schröder, S.; Unglaub, D.; Trost, M.; Cheng, X.; Zhang, J.; Duparré, A. Spectral angle resolved scattering of thin film coatings. *Appl. Opt.* **2014**, *53*, A35–A41. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Bublitz, S.; Mühlig, C. Absolute absorption measurements in optical coatings by laser induced deflection. *Coatings* **2019**, *9*, 473. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Mydlář, M.; Vanda, J.; Mureşan, M.G.; Čech, P.; Brajer, J.; Mocek, T. Mobile LIDT. In Proceedings of the Optics and Measurement International Conference, Liberec, Czech Republic, 8–10 October 2019; p. 11385.
38. *ISO 21254-2:2011; Lasers and Laser-Related Equipment—Test Methods for Laser-Radiation-Induced Damage Threshold—Part 2: Threshold Determination*. International Organization for Standardization: London, UK, 2011.
39. *ISO 21254-3:2011; Lasers and Laser-Related Equipment—Test Methods for Laser-Radiation-Induced Damage Threshold—Part 3: Assurance of Laser Power (Energy) Handling Capabilities*. International Organization for Standardization: London, UK, 2011.
40. *ISO 21254-4:2011; Lasers and Laser-Related Equipment—Test Methods for Laser-Radiation-Induced Damage Threshold—Part 4: Inspection, Detection and Measurement*. International Organization for Standardization: London, UK, 2011.
41. Cheng, X.; Wang, Z. Defect-related properties of optical coatings. *Adv. Opt. Technol.* **2014**, *3*, 65–90. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Xia, S.; Cai, J.; Zhang, X.; Li, J.; Jin, G.; Chang, X. Study on thermal stress of the fused silica irradiated by millisecond–nanosecond combined pulse laser. *Pramana* **2021**, *95*, 1–8. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Negres, R.A.; Norton, M.A.; Cross, D.A.; Carr, C.W. Growth behavior of laser-induced damage on fused silica optics under UV, ns laser irradiation. *Opt. Express* **2010**, *18*, 19966–19976. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
44. Génin, F.Y.; Feit, M.D.; Kozlowski, M.R.; Rubenchik, A.M.; Salleo, A.; Yoshiyama, J. Rear-surface laser damage on 355-nm silica optics owing to Fresnel diffraction on front-surface contamination particles. *Appl. Opt.* **2000**, *39*, 3654–3663. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.